

EFFECT OF MALTING AND SOYBEAN SUPPLEMENTATION ON THE NUTRIENT QUALITY
AND ACCEPTABILITY OF “EKO-EDA”: A MAIZE GRIT PORRIDGE

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ABSTRACT

The effect of malting and soybean supplementation on the nutrient quality and acceptability of maize grit porridge was investigated. Malting of maize and supplementation with soybean significantly ($P<0.05$) increased protein, ash and copper content of *eko-eda* while fat and crude fibre were significantly ($P<0.05$) decreased. Soybean supplementation significantly ($P<0.05$) increased iron and phosphorus content. With the exception of methionine and tryptophan, all essential amino acids were adequate. Maize grit porridge (*eko-eda*) prepared from malted maize grits and blends of maize/soybean grits were acceptable.

KEYWORDS: Malting, supplementation, porridge, essential amino acids, nutrient, quality.

INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays*), the American-Indian word for corn, literally means, “that which sustains life” (FAO, 1997). It is, after wheat and rice, the most important cereal grain in the world providing nutrients for humans and animals and serving as a basic raw material for the production of starch, oil, alcoholic beverages, food sweeteners and more recently, fuel. Maize is an important food in Asia, Africa, Latin America and part of Europe. Each country in these continents has one or more maize dish(es) unique to its culture. Examples are “*kenkey*” in Ghana; *koga* in Cameroun; *injera* in Ethiopia; and *ugali* in Kenya just to mention a few. Likewise in Nigeria, each locality or culture has one or more maize dish(es) unique to its people. An example is “*eko-eda*”.

Eko-eda, a maize grit porridge, is a popular breakfast meal of the Yoruba-Igbomina tribe, natives of Ifelodun and Irepodun Local Government areas of Kwara State in central Nigeria. It is produced by dry milling maize grains into grit and sieving into various particle sizes, any of which can be used depending on individual preferences. The grits are then soaked in water and the hulls and germs removed by decanting. This process gives a cleaner and more acceptable grit which is then steeped in water overnight to soften. The soft maize grits are then cooked in boiling water and allowed to thicken to an acceptable consistency, this also depends on individual preferences. It is then served hot. Sugar (sucrose) may be added to enhance the taste.

Maize constitutes an important source of carbohydrates, protein, B-complex vitamins and minerals. As an energy source, it compares favourably with root/tuber crops and is similar in energy value to dried legumes. Furthermore, it is an excellent source of carbohydrate and is richer in nutrients compared to other cereals. However, maize is deficient in lysine and tryptophan. Many studies conducted with animals have demonstrated that the addition of both amino acids improves the quality of maize protein. The addition of these limiting amino acids has been confirmed to improve the nitrogen balance in children (Bressani *et. al.*, 1968).

Soybeans (*Glycine max*) is rich in both essential and non-essential amino acids. For a plant food, soybean protein is exceptionally rich in lysine and can serve as a valuable supplement to cereal foods where lysine is a limiting factor (FAO/WHO, 1973). Though a valuable source of protein, soybean has certain adverse nutritional effects following consumption of raw soybean meal. This has been attributed to the presence of endogenous inhibitors of digestive enzymes. The full nutritional potential of soybean is attained only after a certain amount of heat has been applied.

Table 1: Chemical composition of maize grits and blends of maize-soybean grits.

Parameter	Grit samples			
	C	MMG	MMSG	MMMSG
Moisture (%)	9.43 ^b	11.76 ^a	8.44 ^d	8.98 ^c
Protein (%)	8.57 ^c	6.89 ^d	17.25 ^b	20.26 ^a
Fat (%)	12.38 ^a	10.70 ^a	8.19 ^b	5.49 ^c
Ash (%)	0.33 ^c	0.45 ^b	0.67 ^a	0.68 ^a
Crude fibre (%)	4.05 ^a	2.38 ^b	2.06 ^b	1.27 ^c
Carbohydrate (%)	65.24 ^b	67.82 ^a	63.39 ^c	63.32 ^c
Calcium (mg/kg)	96.2 ^a	96.4 ^a	96.3 ^a	96.0 ^a
Copper (mg/kg)	4.71 ^c	4.86 ^b	5.26 ^a	5.28 ^a
Iron (mg/kg)	3.4 ^b	3.4 ^b	5.47 ^a	5.49 ^a
Phosphorus (mg/kg)	442.5 ^b	451.1 ^b	563.7 ^a	5573 ^b

Values are means of triplicate determinations, Means in the same row with different superscript are significantly different (p<0.05)

- C = Untreated maize grits (control)
- MMG = Malted maize grits
- MMSG = 70:30 blend of untreated maize grits and malted soybean grits
- MMMSG = 70:30 blend of malted maize and malted soybean grits.

Malting involves the germination of grains until the food store (endosperm) which is available to support the germ has suffered some degradation from enzyme (Briggs and Mac Donald, 1983). During malting, there is an improvement in the nutritional content of grains (Collins and Sanders, 1976). Through the activity of enzymes, some nutrients are degraded (anti nutritional factors inclusive) while others are changed from one form to another.

The objective of this study is to determine the effect of malting and soybean supplementation on the nutritional value (with respect to proximate composition and amino acid content) and acceptability (with respect to sensory properties) of maize grit porridge (*eko-eda*).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Maize grains (white variety) and soybean seeds were obtained from central market, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria on 7th July, 2007.

Preparation of samples

Maize grains and soybean seeds were winnowed and hand picked to remove pieces of cobs, stones, damaged seeds and rodents' droppings. They were then washed with tap water and oven-dried at 60^oC for 1h.

Table 2: Amino acid composition (g/100g) of maize grit and blends of maize-soybeans grits

Grit samples					FAO/WHO (1991) Req.
Amino acid	C	MMG	MMSG	MMMSG	Pattern for 10-12year olds
Essential					
Threonine	3.3±0.00	3.3±0.00	3.7±0.01	3.7±0.00	2.8
Cystine	2.0±0.02	2.0±0.01	1.5±0.00	1.5±0.01	1.2
Valine	4.8±0.00	4.7±0.00	6.3±0.00	6.3±0.01	2.5
Methionine	1.6±0.00	1.6±0.00	1.2±0.00	1.2±0.01	1.3
Isoleucine	4.0±0.01	3.9±0.00	3.8±0.01	3.8±0.02	2.8
Leucine	11.7±0.00	10.9±0.02	7.4±0.00	7.1±0.01	4.4
Tyrosine	3.5±0.02	3.5±0.01	4.6±0.00	4.7±0.02	1.1
Phenylalanine	5.2±0.01	5.0±0.00	5.4±0.02	5.4±0.02	1.0
Lysine	3.1±0.00	3.2±0.01	4.7±0.01	4.7±0.02	4.4
Tryptophan	0.5±0.00	0.5±0.01	0.8±0.00	0.8±0.01	0.9
Non Essential					
Aspartic acid	5.9±0.02	6.1±0.00	7.2±0.02	7.3±0.02	
Serine	4.7±0.01	4.7±0.01	4.8±0.00	4.8±0.02	
Glutamic acid	15.2±0.02	15.3±0.00	16.6±0.02	16.6±0.01	
Proline	7.4±0.01	7.2±0.01	3.3±0.00	3.2±0.00	
Glycine	3.7±0.00	3.7±0.01	3.7±0.00	3.7±0.02	
Histidine	2.6±0.01	2.8±0.02	3.2±0.01	3.1±0.01	
Arginine	5.0±0.00	5.2±0.00	6.9±0.02	6.9±0.01	
Alanine	7.5±0.01	7.5±0.00	8.1±0.02	8.2±0.00	

Values are mean ± SD of triplicate determinations.

- C = Untreated maize grits
- MMG = Malted maize grits
- MMSG = 70:30 blend of untreated maize and malted soybean grits.
- MMMSG = 70: blend of malted maize and malted soybean grits.

Preparation of maize grits

A 500g lot of maize grains were dry milled using a double disc attrition mill. The resultant grits were sieved using a 2mm sieve to obtain the desired grit particle size. This was then soaked in water for 2h to

soften and the germ and hulls were separated from the grits (endosperm) by decanting. The grits were then dried at 100⁰ C for 1h 30 min in an air oven (Gallenkamp, 3000 plus series, England) and packaged in low density polyethylene.

Preparation of malted maize grits

A 500g lot of maize grains were cleaned as described previously. The grains were then soaked for 16h with the soak water been changed after 4h. At the end of soaking, the soak water was drained off and the grains were spread evenly on trays and covered with jute bags in a dark, secluded area for 72 hours at 32± 2⁰C. At the end of malting, the grains were dried at 100⁰C for 1h 30 min in an air oven. After drying, the grains were devegetated, i.e. the rootlets were removed by rubbing between palms after which they were milled, sieved, soaked in water for 2h to soften. The germ and hull were then separated from the grits by decanting. The grits were then dried and packaged as with the previous sample.

Preparation of soybean grits

A 500g lot of soybean seeds were malted, dried at 60⁰C for 1h, milled and packaged as was the case with malted maize grits. Soybean was malted primarily to reduce its characteristic beany flavour.

Formulation of blends

Table 3: Mean sensory scores of *eko-eda* prepared from maize grits and blends of maize and soybean grits

Parameters	C	Samples		
		MMG	MMSG	MMMSG
Appearance	6.40 ^a	6.50 ^a	3.70 ^a	4.60 ^{ab}
Colour	6.30 ^a	6.40 ^a	4.20 ^b	5.10 ^{ab}
Taste	5.80 ^a	6.10 ^a	3.80 ^b	4.20 ^{ab}
O/A	6.10 ^a	6.20 ^a	3.90 ^b	4.20 ^{ab}

Mean values in the same row with different superscripts are significantly different (p<0.05).

KEY

C = Maize grits (control)

MMG = Malted maize grits

MMSG = 70:30 blend of untreated maize grits and malted soybean grits

MMMSG = 70:30 blend of malted maize grits and malted soybean grits.

O/A = Overall acceptability.

Values are based on a 7 – point scale where 7 = like very much and 1 = dislike very much.

Formulation of blends

Malted soybean grits were blended with untreated maize grits in a ratio 30:70 since this was the most organoleptically acceptable level of blending (Ocheme and Alashi, 2007). Malted soybean and malted maize were also blended in the same ratio.

Determination of Chemical Composition

Each sample was analyzed for proximate composition in triplicate. Moisture, protein, fat and ash were determined according to the AOAC (2000) methods. The mineral composition was determined according to the AOAC (1995) method. Amino acid was analyzed according to the method described by Hussain and Basahy (1998). The samples were homogenized in 6ml, 6M HCL for 24h at 110⁰C. After hydrolysis, the hydrolysate was filtered through a G3 glass filter, evaporated in a vacuum at 40⁰C, then diluted with a citrate buffer (pH 3.2) and analyzed using the amino acid analyzer (SYK 3540).

Sensory Evaluation.

Eko-eda was prepared from untreated maize grits; malted maize grits; 30:70 blend of malted soybean grits and untreated maize grits; and 30:70 blend of malted soybean grits and malted maize grits. The products were judged by a 20-member panel consisting of staff and students of the Department of Food Science and Nutrition, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Nigeria. A 7-point hedonic rating scale was used where 7 = like very much and 1 = dislike very much.

Statistical analysis

All data were tested with ANOVA and Duncan multiple range test using the statistical package for social scientist (SPSS, 2000).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the chemical composition of maize grits and blends of maize-soybean grits are shown in Table 1. Malting and supplementation with soybean significantly ($p<0.05$) increased the protein and ash content of the grits while significantly ($p<0.05$) decreasing the fat, crude fibre and carbohydrate content. The increase in protein may be due to the high protein content of soybean which supplemented that of maize while the increase in ash may be due to effect of malting which could have made some hitherto unavailable minerals available due to the degrading action of enzymes. The decrease in fat content may be due to the action of lipolytic enzymes which may have been liberated during malting. It may also be due to utilization of some of the fat to support respiration (Briggs and MacDonald 1983). This reason may also be responsible for the decrease in carbohydrate as a result of malting and supplementation with soybean.

Supplementation with soybean significantly ($p<0.05$) increased the copper, iron and phosphorus content of the grits. Soybean is not a major source of minerals (McGilvery, 1984) but, when included in a mixed diet, contribute to overall requirements.

The amino acid composition of maize grits and blends of maize soybean grits is shown in Table 2. Supplementation with soybean caused the lysine content of grits to meet FAO/WHO (1991) requirement pattern. Supplementation also reduced the leucine content of the grits. This is important since excess leucine interferes with the absorption and utilization of isoleucine (Benton *et al.*, 1956). This will result in a better balance of the amino acids. The amino acid profile of maize-soybean grits shows that methionine and tryptophan are the limiting amino acids while other essential amino acids are adequate.

The mean sensory scores of *eko-eda* prepared from maize grits and blends of maize soybean grits are shown in Table 3. The sensory evaluation result showed that there were significant ($p<0.05$) differences between the *eko-eda* prepared from maize grits and *eko-eda* prepared from soybean grits with respect to colour, taste and overall acceptability. This could be attributed to the colour and flavour of soybeans which may have caused a deviation from the conventional *eko-eda*. However, *eko-eda* prepared from malted maize grits; blends of untreated maize-soybean grits; and malted maize-soybean grits were as acceptable as the control sample.

CONCLUSION

Supplementation with soybean improved the protein, mineral and amino acid content of *eko-eda*. However, methionine and tryptophan were limiting. Furthermore, *eko-eda* prepared from blends of maize and soybean grits were acceptable.

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Received for Publication: 21/02/2008

Accepted for Publication: 13/03/2008

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